

Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Chewable Tooth Tablets

**Saravanan Elangovan¹, Dinesh Kumar Nagarajan², Prem Kumar Sugumar³,
Rahul Saravanan⁴, Stalin Ramanathan⁵, Syed Mohamed Buhari Mohamed
Mydeen*⁶**

^{2,3,4,5,6}B. Pharm, Department of Pharmacy, EGS Pillay College of Pharmacy, Nagapattinam.

¹Saravanan Elangovan, M. Pharm, Associate professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, EGS Pillay college of pharmacy, Nagapattinam.

ABSTRACT

Chewable tooth tablets are an innovative and eco-friendly alternative to conventional tooth tablets, offering convenience, portability and reduced plastic waste, it is future innovative product and it is easy to carry and travel convenience, traditional toothpaste contains large amount of water, increasing manufacturing and transport emissions while tablets are dry and waterless reducing resource uses and carbon footprint. This study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of the chewable tooth tablets using suitable excipients and herbal ingredients to ensure effective oral hygiene. The tablets were prepared by direct compression method using components such as abrasives, binders, sweetness, and active cleansing agent to enhance cleaning efficiency taste and stability. Various quality control test were conducted to evaluate physical and chemical parameters including tablet hardness, friability, weight variation loss on drying, pH, foamability. The results indicated that the formulated tablets were acceptable mechanical strength, low friability, neutral pH, satisfactory foaming capacity, good stability, ensuring safe and effective use. Sensory evaluation showed that the tablets had as slightly spicy-herbal and slightly bitter taste and acceptable mouth feel, improving consumer compliance. Overall, the study demonstrates that chewable tooth tablets are a promising, user friendly and sustainable with potential for the commercial development and further optimization in oral care application.

Keywords: Herbal chewable tooth tablets, Oral hygiene, Medicinal plants, Antimicrobial activity, Formulation and evaluation, Natural oral care.

INTRODUCTION

Chewable toothpaste tablets are tiny little circular discs that resemble breath mints and are made entirely of natural components that are designed to keep your teeth clean by eradicating plaque^[1]. Once in your mouth, you will crush the tablet with your teeth, usually your larger and stronger back molars. The dry components of toothpaste in tablet form are referred to as toothpaste tablets^[2]. Simply place it in your mouth, moisten your toothbrush, and agitate the tablet with the bristles like you would a cleanser. The cleaning benefits are the same as toothpaste and no messy pastes and it's sustainable too. Tabs being dry there is minimal or no preservatives at all and hence

it's safe and eco-friendly. Being in tablets form they are easy to transport hence low carbon footprint^[3]. Sometimes toothpaste might get ripped or squeezed out which will not happen with tablets. They are easy to store, and while travelling no messy sticky pastes or even dripping on bathroom floors or even dried pieces falling off. They are in pre-portioned sizes so no wastage as the exact amount is being used, tooth tablets are a safer and better option. More than anything hygiene no passing of germs when the tube is swiped from brush to brush. Our mouths throughout the day go from re-mineralisation to demineralization. For the natural remineralisation to occur the mouth should not be in an acidic state but in an alkaline state^[4]. The proposed research tooth tablets recommend

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

just crushing a tablet in your mouth and swishing for 10 to 15 seconds for a quick alkalizing after a meal or coffee can keep your teeth clean ^[5].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

S.NO	INGREDIENTS	CATEGORY	PERCENTAGE (%w/w)	USES
1	Clove (Syzygium aromaticum) ^[6]	Herbal active ingredients	3%	Analgesic, Relieves toothache
2	Yellow berried night shade ^[7] (Solanum surattense Burm)	Herbal active ingredients	3%	Improves gum health, Anti-inflammatory
3	Indian long pepper (Piper longum L) ^[8]	Herbal active ingredients	3%	Enhance Antimicrobial action
4	Chaff flower (Achyranthes aspera Linn.) ^[9]	Herbal active ingredients	3.4%	Helps to control dental plaque, promote overall oral hygiene
5	Dry ginger (Zingiber officinale Roscoe) ^[10]	Herbal active ingredients	3%	Anti-inflammatory, reduce tooth pain
6	Turmeric (Curcuma longa Linn) ^[11]	Herbal active ingredients	3.5%	Antibacterial, Anti inflammatory
7	Moringa (Moringa oleifera Lam.) ^[12]	Herbal active ingredients	4%	Gum strengthening
8	Cinnamon (Cinnamomum verum) ^[13]	Herbal active ingredients	3%	Breath freshener
9	Charcoal	Adsorbent	3%	Absorbs toxins and whitening teeth
10	Salt	Mild Abrasive	0.6%	Plaque control
11	Calcium carbonate	Abrasive	35%	Removes dental plaque and surface stains
12	Mannitol	Sweetening Agent	15%	Provide sweet taste to the tablet
13	Micro crystalline cellulose	Binder/Diluent	12.5%	Provide tablet strength and bulk
14	Carboxy methyl cellulose	Binder	3%	Helps tablet break down quickly in mouth
15	Talc	Glidant	2%	Improves powder flow
16	Magnesium stearate	Lubricant	1.5%	Prevents sticking during compression
17	Sodium lauryl sulphate	Surfactant	1.5%	Foaming agent

PREPARATION OF TABLETS BY DIRECT COMPRESSION METHOD

Procedure:

All herbal powders and excipients were accurately weighed according to the formulation. The weighed powders are passed through sieve No.60# to obtain uniform particle size. The active ingredients are mixed thoroughly with diluents and binders to ensure uniform distribution. Disintegrant and surfactant are

added and mixed properly. Lubricant and glidant are added last and blended gently to avoid over-mixing. The final blend is evaluated for flow properties. The powder blend is then compressed into tablets using a single-punch by direct compression method and the punched tablets can be evaluated as per IP specification.^[14]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

PREFORMULATION FACTORS:

1. Angle of repose

Figure: Angle of repose of powder

✧ $\tan \theta = h/r$

✧ $\theta = \tan^{-1}(h/r)$

S.No	Height of the pile(h)	Diameter of pile(d)	Radius(r)	$\frac{h}{r}$	Angle of repose $\theta = \tan^{-1} \frac{h}{r}$
1	2.4 cm	6.6 cm	3.3 cm	0.73	36.11°
2	2.2 cm	6.4 cm	3.2 cm	0.67	33.82°
3	2.1 cm	6.5 cm	3.25 cm	0.66	33.42°

$$\theta = \frac{\theta_1 + \theta_2 + \theta_3}{3}$$

$$= \frac{36.11 + 33.82 + 33.42}{3}$$

$$= \frac{103.35}{3}$$

$$= 34.45^\circ$$

Inference: the angle of repose for the powder is found to be 34.45°.so, the powder has **good flow property**

2. Bulk Density

Figure: Bulk density of powder

$$\text{Bulk density} = \frac{\text{mass}}{\text{bulk volume}}$$

$$\text{bulk density 1} = \frac{10}{25}$$

$$= 0.40 \text{ g/ml}$$

$$\text{bulk density 2} = \frac{10}{23}$$

$$= 0.43 \text{ g/ml}$$

$$\text{bulk density 3} = \frac{10}{24}$$

$$= 0.42 \text{ g/ml}$$

$$\text{Average bulk density} = 0.41 \text{ g/ml}$$

3. Tapped Density

Figure : Tapped density of powder

$$\text{Tapped density} = \frac{\text{mass}}{\text{tapped volume}}$$

$$\text{Tapped density 1} = \frac{10}{19}$$

$$= 0.52 \text{ g/ml}$$

$$\text{Tapped density 2} = \frac{10}{17}$$

$$= 0.58 \text{ g/ml}$$

$$\text{Tapped density 3} = \frac{10}{18}$$

$$= 0.55 \text{ g/ml}$$

$$\text{Average Tapped density} = 0.55 \text{ g/ml}$$

4. Carr's Index

$$\% \text{compressibility index} = \frac{\text{tapped density} - \text{bulk density}}{\text{tapped density}} \times 100$$

$$c_1 = \left[1 - \frac{0.40}{0.52} \right] \times 100$$

$$= [1 - 0.76] \times 100$$

$$= 0.24 \times 100$$

$$= 24\%$$

$$c_2 = \left[1 - \frac{0.43}{0.58} \right] \times 100$$

$$= [1 - 0.74] \times 100$$

$$= 0.26 \times 100$$

$$= 26\%$$

$$c_3 = \left[1 - \frac{0.42}{0.55} \right] \times 100$$

$$= [1 - 0.76] \times 100$$

$$= 0.24 \times 100$$

$$= 24\%$$

$$\text{Average Compressibility index} = 24.6\%$$

Inference : Compressibility index or Carr's index of a powder is found to be 24.6%.so, the powder has **passable flow**.

5. Hausner Ratio

$$\text{Hausner ratio} = \frac{\text{tapped density}}{\text{bulk density}}$$

$$H_1 = \frac{0.52}{0.40} = 1.3$$

$$H_2 = \frac{0.58}{0.43} = 1.1$$

$$H_3 = \frac{0.55}{0.42} = 1.3$$

$$\text{Average Hausner's ratio} = 1.2$$

Inference: Hausner's ratio of powder is found to be 1.2, so, the powder has **passable flow**.
 ✧ Odour : Pleasant odour

✧ Taste : Slightly spicy-herbal and slightly bitter taste

POST FORMULATION FACTORS:

1. Organoleptic evaluations

✧ Colour: Ash colour

2. Thickness & Diameter

No of tablets	Thickness	Diameter
1	0.6cm	0.9 cm
2	0.6cm	0.9 cm
3	0.6cm	0.9 cm
4	0.6cm	0.9 cm
5	0.6cm	0.9 cm
6	0.6cm	0.9 cm
7	0.6cm	0.9 cm
8	0.6cm	0.9 cm
9	0.6cm	0.9 cm
10	0.6cm	0.9 cm

3. Hardness Test

No of tablets	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Monsanto(kg/cm ²)	3.1	3.5	3.2	3.2	3.0	3.5	3.3	3.4	3.5	3.2
P-fizzer(kg/cm ²)	6.2	6.0	5.8	5.5	5.6	6.1	5.5	5.8	5.6	6.0

4. Average Weight & Weight Variation (IP)

$$\text{Percentage Deviation} = \frac{\text{weight of each tablet} - \text{Average weight of tablet}}{\text{Average weight of tablet}} \times 100$$

No of tablets	Individual weight of Tablets	Percentage deviation
1	0.65 g	+4.17%
2	0.62 g	- 0.64%
3	0.64 g	+2.56%
4	0.63 g	+0.96%
5	0.63 g	+0.96%
6	0.64 g	+2.56%
7	0.61 g	-2.24%
8	0.62 g	- 0.64%
9	0.63 g	+0.96%
10	0.60 g	-3.85%
11	0.61 g	-2.24%
12	0.63 g	+0.96%
13	0.61 g	-2.24%
14	0.65 g	+4.17%
15	0.62 g	- 0.64%
16	0.64 g	+2.56%
17	0.62 g	- 0.64%
18	0.61 g	-2.24%

19	0.62 g	- 0.64%
20	0.60 g	-3.85%

Inference: The percentage deviation of individual tablet weights ranged from -3.85% to +4.17%. All the tablets were within the acceptable pharmacopoeia limit of ±5% for tablets weighing more than 250 mg. Hence, the tablet formulation passed the weight variation test as per Indian Pharmacopoeia standards.

$$\% \text{ Friability} = \frac{w1-w2}{w1} \times 100$$

$$\% \text{ Friability} = \frac{6.58-6.57}{6.58} \times 100$$

$$= \frac{0.01}{6.58} \times 100$$

$$= 0.152 \%$$

5. Friability Test (IP)

Calculation:

Figure: Weight of 10 tablets before and after the friability test

Inference: The friability of the toothpaste tablets was found to be 0.152%, which is within the acceptable pharmacopoeia limit of not more than 1.0% as

specified by the Indian Pharmacopoeia and United States Pharmacopoeia.

6. Disintegration Test

No of tablets	1	2	3	4	5	6
Time	3.00 minutes	3minutes 12 seconds	3minutes 29 seconds	3minutes 31 seconds	3minutes 40 seconds	4minutes 20 seconds

7. pH of Solution.

Figure : pH of tooth tablet

Inference: The toothpaste tablet solution with a pH of 7.11 is nearly neutral, which is ideal and acceptable for oral use.

8. Foaming Ability

Figure: Foam volume

$$\text{Foam ability} = \frac{\text{Foam volume}}{\text{Initial liquid volume}} \times 100$$

- ❖ Initial liquid volume = 11 ml
- ❖ Foam volume = 31ml

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Foam ability} &= \frac{31}{11} \times 100 \\ &= 2.82 \times 100 \\ &= 282\% \end{aligned}$$

Inference: The toothpaste tablet shows **good** foaming ability.

9. Moisture Content (Loss on Drying – IP)

Figure: Final weight of powder

$$\text{loss on drying} = \frac{\text{initial weight} - \text{final weight}}{\text{initial weight}} \times 100$$

- ❖ Initial weight = 63.10 gm
- ❖ Final weight = 62.03 gm

$$\begin{aligned} \text{loss on drying} &= \frac{63.10 - 62.03}{63.10} \times 100 \\ &= \frac{1.07}{63.10} \times 100 \\ &= 0.0169 \times 100 \end{aligned}$$

LOD= 1.69%

Inference:

The Loss on Drying (LOD) of the prepared formulation was found to be 1.69%. This low LOD value indicates that the formulation contains minimal moisture and volatile matter. The result confirms that the powder blend is well dried and physically stable.

10. Stability Studies

Test	15 days	30 days	45 days
Appearance	Good	Good	Good
pH	7.11	7.11	7.11
Friability	0.152%	0.165%	0.170%
Hardness (Monsanto)	3.29kg/cm ²	3.01kg/cm ²	2.80kg/cm ²

DENTAL EVALUATION OF TOOTH TABLETS: 1.Stain Removal Test (Cleaning Efficiency Test)

Figure: Normal egg shell

Figure: Egg shell stain with coffee

Figure : Toothpaste slurry preparation

Figure: Brushing the stained egg shell

Figure : After washing the egg shell

2. Abrasiveness Test

Figure: Initial weight of egg shell

Figure: Brushing the egg shell by using tooth paste slurry

Figure: Final weight of egg shell

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully formulated and evaluated chewable toothpaste tablets as an innovative and eco-friendly alternative to conventional tooth paste. The prepared tablets demonstrated acceptable physical characteristics, including uniform weight variation, adequate hardness, low friability and satisfactory disintegration time, indicating good mechanical strength and consumer suitability. The formulated tablets showed effective cleansing performance, optimal foaming ability, suitable pH compatible with oral tissue and satisfactory antimicrobial activity against oral pathogens. Loss on drying and moisture content within acceptable limits, and stain removable test are done on the egg shell, suggesting good stability and self-life potential. The use of biodegradable excipients and the elimination of plastic packaging further highlights the environmental benefits of this formulation.

Overall, chewable toothpaste tablets represent a promising, portable and sustainable oral hygiene product with effective dental cleaning performance and improve consumer convenience. Further studies may focus on long term stability, flavour optimization large scale production, and clinical evaluation to further validate product safety, efficacy and commercial feasibility.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to express our heartfelt thanks to our guide, principal and teachers for their valuable guidance and continuous support in completing this article. We also thank our institution for providing the required facilities. Our sincere appreciation goes to our friends for their cooperation and to our parents for their encouragement and blessings.

REFERENCES

1. DeoreNisha N., R. K. Surawase A Chewable Toothpaste Tablet: An Alternative approach to the Toothpaste.
2. An_Alternative_Approach_to_Waste_Management_A_Study_on_Toothpaste. ResearchGate available from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344071657>
3. Asha M. Jagtap, Sudhir R. Kaulage, Shivam S. Kanse, Vishal D. Shelke, Akshata S. Gavade, Ganesh B. Vambhurkar, Rohit R. Todkar, Vidya N. Dange. Preparation and Evaluation of Toothpaste. Asian J. Pharm. Ana. 2018.
4. Monika SahebraoTambe Priyanka PradeepTandel, Manish MukeshVaishnav. A Review on Tooth Paste, International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews, Vol 4, no 4, pp 805-808 April 2023.
5. Ankita. J. Patel*, Jaivin. V. Chauhan Tooth Tablets: A Review of Formulation Consideration International journal of pharma professionals research Volume – 14, Issue – 4, October – 2023.
6. Sari, DK, Nining Sugihartini, Tedjo Yuwono, 2015, Irritation Test And Physical Properties Evaluation Of Essential Oils Clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*) In Emulgel, Fakultas Farmasi Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, diakses tanggal 7 February 2018.
7. Singh OM, Singh TP (2010) Phytochemistry of *Solanum xanthocarpum*: An amazing traditional healer. J Sci Ind Res 69: 732-740.
8. Pei YQ. A review of pharmacology and clinical use of piperine and its derivatives. Epilepsia 1983;24:177-82
9. Basu NK, Singh HK and Aggarwal OP: Chemical investigation of *Achyranthes aspera*, J. Pro. Inst .Chem. 2007; 29 (1): 33-58.
10. Q.-Q. Mao, X.-Y. Xu, S.-Y. Cao, R.-Y. Gan, H. Corke, T. Beta, H.-B. Li, Bioactive compounds and bioactivities of ginger (*zingiber officinale* Roscoe), Foods 8 (2019) 185.
11. Curucuma Longa. Alternative Medicine Review Monograph; 2002:119-125. Available from: http://www.awl.ch/heilpflanzen/curcuma_longa/Curcuma_en.pdf.
12. Mohanty M, Mohanty S, Bhuyan SK, Bhuyan R. Phytoperspective of *Moringa oleifera* for oral health care: An innovative ethnomedicinal approach. Phytother Res. 2021;35(3):1345-57. doi: 10.1002/ptr.6896.
13. Rao, P.V.; Gan, S.H. Cinnamon: A multifaceted medicinal plant. Evid. Based Complementary Altern. Med. 2014, 642942
14. The Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission. The Indian Pharmacopoeia, Ghaziabad: Government of India, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, (2018) 247,947,1452,2371. (2014) volume-1 (190-230), (2022) volume-1(350-390).

HOW TO CITE: Saravanan Elangovan, Dinesh Kumar Nagarajan, Prem Kumar Sugumar, Rahul Saravanan, Stalin Ramanathan, Syed Mohamed Buhari Mohamed Mydeen*, Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Chewable Tooth Tablets, J. Pharm. Sci., 2026, 2 (3), 287-296. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19053987>

